

Administrative Support as Moderator on Teachers' Professional Life and Instructional Behavior

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Abstract. The study aimed to determine the moderating effect of administrative support on the interaction between teachers' professional life and instructional behavior. The respondents comprised 197 elementary school teachers from Panabo Central District in Panabo City, selected through stratified random sampling. Non-experimental quantitative research design using descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Partial Correlation, and Hierarchical Regression Analysis. The findings revealed that teachers' professional life and instructional behavior received moderately extensive ratings, while administrative support was rated as extensive. A significant relationship was found between teachers' professional life and their instructional behavior, with the administrative backing serving as a significant moderator in this interaction. It is recommended that school administrators enhance their support for teachers by providing more resources, fostering a positive school climate, and offering continuous professional development opportunities to ensure consistent and effective administrative support.

KEY WORDS

1. instructional behavior 2. professional life 3. administrative support

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1. Introduction

The effectiveness of teachers in the classroom is influenced by a multitude of factors, among which administrative support plays a pivotal role. Administrative support encompasses the guidance, resources, and encouragement provided by school leadership to foster a conducive environment for professional growth and instructional excellence. As educators navigate the complexities of teaching, the degree of support they receive can significantly impact their professional satisfaction, motivation, and instructional practices. This relationship suggests that administrative support may serve as a crucial moderator, potentially amplifying or mitigating the effects of various factors on teachers' professional lives and their instructional behavior. Understanding this dynamic is essential for developing strategies that enhance teacher performance and, ultimately, student achievement. Moreover, the idea that administrative support has a crucial moderating effect on the relationship between teachers' professional lives and their instructional behavior is a valid and important concept in education, as it helps explain how a supportive administrative environment can positively influence a

teacher's performance and job satisfaction, ultimately leading to better educational outcomes. Globally, in the United States, one of the prominent challenges affecting teachers' instructional behavior is the growing diversity in classrooms. Teachers often struggle to address the varied cultural backgrounds, languages, and learning needs of students (Gay, 2018). This challenge necessitates culturally responsive teaching practices, which many educators feel unprepared to implement effectively. Furthermore, standardized testing and accountability measures have led to a narrowed curriculum focus, often limiting teachers' ability to employ innovative and student-centered instructional strategies. These pressures can result in teaching to the test rather than fostering critical thinking and creativity among students (Hursh, 2018). Another significant issue is the pervasive impact of socioeconomic disparities on instructional behavior. Teachers in low-income areas often face larger class sizes, fewer resources, and higher rates of student absenteeism, which can impede effective teaching (Ladd, 2019). In many Arabian countries, one of the primary challenges impacting instructional behavior is the rigid adherence to traditional teaching methods. Despite ongoing educational reforms, lecture-based instruction remains prevalent, limiting opportunities for student engagement and critical thinking (Al-Issa, 2019). This traditional approach often clashes with the need to develop 21st-century skills, such as problem-solving and creativity, in students. Moreover, the educational systems in these countries are sometimes criticized for their heavy reliance on rote memorization and high-stakes examinations, which can stifle teachers' instructional flexibility and innovation (Zyoud, 2020). In various Asian countries, instructional behavior is often influenced by high societal expectations and the competitive nature of the educational environment. Countries like South Korea and Japan are known for their rigorous academic standards, where teachers are under constant pressure to ensure their students excel in standardized tests (Byun, 2021). This pressure can lead to a focus on test preparation over holistic educational practices, impacting the breadth and depth of instruction. Teachers may feel compelled to prioritize content coverage and examination techniques over fostering critical thinking and creativity (Kang, 2019). In countries such as India and China, teachers often manage classrooms with 40 or more students, making it challenging to implement personalized instruction and active learning strategies (Dong, 2020). Moreover, Cabanilla (2019) noted that the instructional behavior of teachers in the Philippines faces several significant issues that impede effective teaching and learning. One major issue is the lack of adequate professional development opportunities. Many teachers lack access to continuous training, which is essential for keeping up with the evolving educational methodologies and technologies. The scarcity of professional development programs leaves teachers using outdated instructional strategies, which may not effectively engage students or address their diverse learning needs. Another pressing issue is the inadequate support and resources provided to teachers, which significantly impacts their instructional behavior. Despite the recognition of education as a priority, the budget allocated for educational resources in many regions remains insufficient (David, Albert, Vizmanos, 2019). Despite numerous studies examining the relationship between teachers' professional life and their instructional behavior, a significant research gap exists regarding the moderating effect of administrative support on this relationship. Most of the research encountered by the investigator primarily focuses on the direct influence of teachers' professional life aspects—such as job satisfaction, burnout, and professional development—on their instructional behavior. These studies offer valuable insights into how factors such as motivation and

emotional well-being directly influence teaching practices. However, they often overlook the potential role that administrative support might play in shaping this dynamic. Understanding whether and how administrative support can enhance or mitigate the influence of professional life on instructional behavior remains unexplored, thus presenting a critical gap in the existing literature. Moreover, the majority of these studies have been conducted in foreign settings, particularly in Western countries, where educational systems and cultural contexts differ significantly from those in the Philippines. The lack of localized research means that findings from these foreign studies may not be directly applicable to the Philippine context due to variations in educational policies, administrative structures, and socio-cultural factors. Notably, the researcher has not encountered any studies specifically examining this moderating effect within the Philippine setting. This absence highlights a crucial gap, as administrative support in Filipino schools might have unique characteristics and implications for teachers' professional lives and instructional behavior. Therefore, there is a pressing need for research that investigates this relationship within the Philippine context to develop more contextually relevant insights and recommendations for enhancing educational outcomes. In the local context, particularly in Panabo Central District, Panabo City, administrative support serves as a vital moderator that significantly influences teachers' professional lives and instructional behaviors. Effective school leadership fosters a positive environment by providing resources, guidance, and constructive feedback, which boosts teachers' morale and encourages ongoing professional development. Such support enables teachers to adopt innovative teaching strategies, address classroom challenges, and improve their instructional practices, ultimately enhancing student learning outcomes. By actively mediating between district policies

and classroom realities, administrators help create an environment where teachers feel valued and empowered, leading to more effective teaching and a higher quality of education within the community.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—This study was guided by theories, such as the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model, and the principles of Instructional Leadership support that administrative support acts as a moderating factor, buffering the negative effects of professional life challenges (such as stress and workload) on instructional behavior by providing job resources. Administrative support also enhances teacher well-being and job satisfaction, which in turn fosters a favorable school climate and improves instructional effectiveness, reinforcing the positive link between professional commitment and actual teaching practices. The present study was based on Skaalvik and Skaalvik's (2017) assertion that administrators who offer resources, clear communication, and emotional support contribute to creating a supportive work environment. Teachers who feel backed by their administration experience increased job satisfaction and reduced stress, leading to more effective teaching practices. This support enables teachers to concentrate on their instructional responsibilities without being overwhelmed by stress and dissatisfaction. In support, Leithwood et al. (2019) suggested that schools fostering a collaborative and respectful environment motivate teachers to invest more in their instructional practices. Effective school leadership fosters a positive school climate, which in turn supports both teaching and learning. When teachers feel appreciated and integrated into a supportive community, they are more inclined to demonstrate positive instructional behaviors. In the context of the current study, it was assumed that administrators who ensure that teachers have the necessary resources—such as instructional materials, technology, and classroom sup-

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

plies—empower teachers to deliver high-quality education. Access to these resources enables teachers to implement diverse and innovative teaching strategies, thereby enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes. Moreover, having adequate resources reduces the time and effort teachers need to spend on acquiring materials independently, thereby alleviating stress. Moreover, administrative support plays a crucial role in enhancing teachers’ engagement with their instructional practices. As shown in Figure 1, the study consists of two variables. The independent variable of the study is professional life, which encompasses career experi-

ences, roles, and responsibilities, interactions with colleagues and students, professional development, and overall job satisfaction. According to Stromquist (2018) quality of professional life is measured in terms of compassion satisfaction or the positive feelings derived from helping others and finding fulfillment in one’s professional role, particularly in caring professions like teaching; revitalization or the process of re-energizing and renewing one’s enthusiasm and commitment to their profession; and comforting thoughts or positive reflections and reassuring beliefs that teachers hold about their profession, their role, and their impact on students.

2. Methodology

This study section outlined the systematic approach employed to investigate the research problem. A descriptive research design was utilized to provide an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon under study. This approach enabled the comprehensive collection of relevant data to address the

research objectives effectively. The selection of participants, tools, and procedures was carefully considered to ensure reliability and validity. The process involved defining the target respondents, designing appropriate research instruments, and establishing a structured data gathering procedure. Data analysis techniques were then applied to interpret the collected information and generate meaningful insights.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher employed a quantitative research approach, specifically the descriptive-correlational technique with mediation analysis, to collect data, ideas, facts, and information relevant to the study. As defined by Ahmad et al. (2019), quantitative research methodologies and strategies systematically and impartially gather and analyze numerical data to understand phenomena, correlations, or trends. These methods involved statistical analysis to derive insights and draw conclusions from the data. Quantitative research entailed collecting and analyzing numerical data within a structured framework to explore various aspects of phenomena, relationships, or patterns. As noted by Mohajan (2020), descriptive research techniques encompass methods used to depict, observe, and analyze the characteristics, behaviors, or phenomena of interest without manipulation or influence. The primary objective was to present a comprehensive portrayal of the subject under study, focusing on describing existing conditions rather than investigating causality. Additionally, descriptive research allowed researchers to outline and characterize various attributes, traits, or features of a population, group, or phenomenon, including demographic details, behaviors, attitudes, and other relevant factors. As defined by Hassan (2024), a correlational research design is a type of non-experimental research used to explore the relationship between two or more variables. This approach involved assessing the extent to which changes in one variable coincided with changes in another, without manipulating either variable. The objective was to determine whether a statistical correlation existed between the variables

and to understand the direction and strength of this relationship. Correlational research served as a crucial tool for advancing knowledge in various fields by uncovering connections between variables, generating hypotheses, and informing practical applications and interventions. Moreover, moderation analysis was a statistical technique used to examine if the relationship between two variables (independent and dependent) changes as a function of a third variable, known as the moderator. It helps in understanding the conditions under which specific effects occur, revealing if the strength or direction of the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable is influenced by the moderator variable. This technique provides insights into the conditions under which specific effects occur, offering a deeper understanding of complex relationships in various research contexts, including educational studies examining the interplay between professional life, administrative support, and instructional behavior (Jérolon et al., 2021). Correlational analysis with a moderation approach was suitable when researchers aimed to explore the interaction between variables and understand the underlying mechanisms. In this context, if the goal was to investigate how administrative support moderated the interaction between professional life and instructional behavior of teachers, a correlational approach could provide valuable insights into these complex dynamics.

2.2. Ethical Consideration—The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study, following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The

survey questionnaires, along with supporting authors, were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. Social Value. Administrative support grounded in ethical principles fosters trust, fairness, and respect within the school community. Upholding integrity and transparency ensure that teachers feel valued and protected, promoting a positive and equitable environment that benefits both educators and students. Informed Consent. Informed consent was a fundamental ethical requirement in research, ensuring that participants were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits before they agreed to participate. In this study on the moderating effect of administrative support on the relationship between teachers' professional life and instructional behavior, the researcher implemented informed consent by providing all potential participants with detailed information about the study. This included the objectives, the types of data to be collected, how the data would be used, and any potential risks or benefits associated with participation. Participants were allowed to ask questions and were required to sign a consent form indicating their voluntary agreement to participate. The researcher ensured that this process was straightforward and transparent, respecting the autonomy of the participants. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The researcher took special care to address the vulnerability of research respondents, particularly because the study involved teachers who might feel pressured to participate due to hierarchical structures in educational institutions. To mitigate this, participation was made entirely voluntary, with assurances that non-participation would not result in any negative consequences. Additionally, the researcher provided clear communication that respondents could withdraw from the study at any time without any repercussions. The researcher also

conducted sensitively, respecting the teachers' professional and personal boundaries. Privacy and Confidentiality. This study examined the data Privacy Provisions of the 2012 Data Privacy Act. Protecting the privacy and confidentiality of participants was a key consideration in this study. The researcher implemented measures to ensure that all data collected were kept confidential and used solely for the purpose of the research. Personal identifiers were removed, and data were anonymized to prevent the identification of individual participants. The researcher also stored data securely, using password-protected files and, where necessary, encrypted storage solutions. Participants were informed about these measures and assured that their responses would remain confidential, thereby fostering an environment of trust and openness.

2.3. Research Respondents—The respondents of the study were the elementary school teachers in Panabo Central District, Panabo City. In this study, the 197 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling was a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. According to Shi (2015), in stratified random sampling, also known as stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics, such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling is appropriate in this study because there is heterogeneity in a population that can be classified with ancillary information. In this study, the inclusion criteria consisted of: licensed, permanent elementary school teachers in Panabo Central District with at least three years (3) of teaching experience; those who regularly interact with administrative support staff involved in their professional development and instruction within the past year; teachers who have no ongoing administrative or criminal cases; and those who voluntarily signed the informed consent

form. The study focused on teachers’ professional experiences, without considering gender or socio-economic status, to ensure that participants could provide relevant information on the influence of administrative support as a moderator on their professional lives and instructional behavior.

2.4. *Research Instrument*—The study employed questionnaires adapted from various studies and modified to fit the context of the respondents in this study. The instrument was divided into two parts. The first part of the in-

strument, adapted from Stamm’s (2012) study, was used to measure the professional quality of life of teachers, which consists of three domains: compassion satisfaction, revitalization, and comforting thoughts. The reliability of the new scale was assessed using a Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.917, which is described as excellent, indicating high reliability and consistency among the items. As a guide in determining the extent of professional life, the researcher made use of the range of means, description, and interpretation as presented below:

Scale for Interpreting the Professional Life of Teachers

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The professional life of teachers is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The professional life of teachers is often observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The professional life of teachers is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The professional life of teachers is seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The professional life of teachers is never observed.

The second part of the instrument was the instructional behavior, which was divided into three domains: avoidance of negative, caring, and repressive. The researcher modified the questionnaire by grouping all items in each dimension under their respective domains. Respondents used a 5-point Likert scale when responding to the questionnaire. The reliability

of the new scale was assessed using a Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.910, which is described as excellent, indicating high reliability and consistency among the items. As a guide in determining the level of instructional behavior, the researcher made use of the range of means, description, and interpretation as presented below:

The third part is about instructional support, adapted from Ye’s (2016) study, which consisted of statements. In answering the questionnaire, the respondents used the 5-Likert scale. The reliability of the new scale was assessed using a Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.966, which

is described as excellent, indicating high reliability and consistency among the items. As a guide in determining the extent of supportive school culture, the researcher made use of the range of means, description, and interpretation as presented below:

2.5. *Data Gathering Procedure*—

Scale for Interpreting Instructional Behavior

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	Instructional behavior is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Instructional behavior is often manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Instructional behavior is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Instructional behavior is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Instructional behavior is never manifested.

Scale for Interpreting Administrative Support

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The administrative support is always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The administrative support is often evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The administrative support is sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The administrative support is rarely evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The administrative support is never evident.

The researcher took steps to conduct the study after validating the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The study was conducted in the second quarter of S.Y. 2022-2023. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the schools division superintendent, and then to the school principals of the selected public schools in Panabo Central District, Panabo City. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. The

researcher proceeded to distribute the research instrument to the respondents after approval to conduct the study. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the administration of the questionnaire, the researcher distributed the questionnaires simultaneously. The respondents were given sufficient time to finish the survey for their convenience. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After retrieving the data from the questionnaire, the scores of each respondent were tallied to organize the data by indicator. Afterward, each score was subjected to both descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the professional life, instructional behavior, and administrative

support in Panabo Central District, Panabo City. This was used to supply the answer for objectives 1, 2, and 3. Partial Correlation Analysis. It was used in this study to assess the significant relationship between independent (pro-

professional life) and dependent (instructional behavior) with moderator (administrative support) variables. Hierarchical Regression Analysis. It was applied to evaluate the moderating effect

of administrative support on the relationship between professional life and instructional behavior of teachers.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study’s objectives, as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extents of professional life, instructional behavior, and administrative support of teachers; the significant relationship between professional life and instructional behavior of teachers in Panabo Central District in Panabo City when moderated by administrative support; and the moderating effect of administrative support on the interaction between professional life and instructional behavior of teachers.

3.1. *Professional Life of Teachers in Panabo Central District, Panabo City*—Table 1 presents a summary of the professional lives of teachers. The overall mean of teachers’ professional life is 3.29, which is described as moderately extensive. This suggests a balance be-

tween positive and negative experiences. This implies that while teachers may find some aspects of their job rewarding, they also encounter challenges that prevent them from experiencing high levels of job satisfaction and professional fulfillment.

Table 1. Summary on Professional Life of Teachers in Panabo Central District, Panabo City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Compassion Satisfaction	3.23	Moderately Extensive
Revitalization	3.37	Moderately Extensive
Comforting Thoughts	3.28	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.29	Moderately Extensive

The findings align with Darling-Hammond et al. (2017), suggesting that moderate levels of professional life imply that teachers do have access to training and learning opportunities. However, these may not be fully comprehensive or specifically tailored to their needs. Effective professional development is essential for teacher growth and job satisfaction, necessitating a continuous, collaborative, and closely connected approach to teachers’ daily work. When such opportunities are available but not optimal, teachers might feel competent but still under-challenged or insufficiently supported in their

professional growth.

3.2. *Teachers’ Instructional Behavior*—Table 2 shows the summary of teachers’ instructional behavior in Panabo Central District, Panabo City. As shown in the table, teachers’ instructional behavior obtained an overall mean score of 3.32, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested. This shows that teachers employ effective strategies and techniques, but do not fully optimize these practices to their highest potential. This level indicates that while teachers are competent and deliver quality instruction, there may still be

areas for improvement in terms of consistency, innovation, and responsiveness to student needs.

Table 2. Summary of Teachers’ Instructional Behavior in Panabo Central District, Panabo City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Avoidance of Negative	3.35	Moderately Extensive
Caring	2.99	Moderately Extensive
Repressive	3.62	Extensive
Overall	3.32	Moderately Extensive

This aligns with Hattie’s (2018) findings that moderate levels of instructional behavior positively influence student outcomes. Teachers operating at this level are competent and able to provide effective instruction that meets educational standards. Even slight enhancements in teaching practices can have a significant impact on student achievement. Thus, acknowledging and supporting moderate instructional behavior is crucial for overall educational success.

3.3. *Administrative Support*—As shown in Table 3, administrative support has a category mean of 3.50, which is described as extensive and is often evident to teachers. Administrative support ensures that teachers have access to essential resources, such as teaching materials, technology, and classroom supplies. While this support may not be comprehensive, it is sufficient to help teachers perform their duties effectively. According to Phyu and Banks (2018), when teachers receive adequate support, they

are better equipped to focus on instructional strategies and student engagement. Supportive leadership has a positive impact on teacher performance and student achievement. Administrators who provide clear guidance, resources, and constructive feedback enable teachers to refine their practices and improve classroom outcomes. Adding on, the mean ratings of the different items range from 2.28 to 4.25. Specifically, the item “Having sufficient access to instructional technology, including computers, printers, software, and internet access” has a mean rating of 2.28, described as less extensive and interpreted as an item that is rarely evident among elementary school teachers. Whereas, the item “Having a school climate created by a strong leadership team and support from the staff helps to create a positive environment in which to teach” reflects a mean rating of 4.25, described as very extensive and interpreted as an item that is always evident.

Emotional support from administrators helps teachers feel valued and understood. This can include regular check-ins, acknowledging teachers’ efforts, and establishing an open-door policy that allows teachers to feel comfortable discussing their concerns. As noted by Saleem et al. (2020), administrative support can provide a buffer against these stressors by offering emotional support, mentorship programs, and

a supportive work environment. Teacher well-being is closely tied to their effectiveness and retention. Administrators who foster a culture of care and support help teachers manage stress, maintain their motivation, and remain committed.

3.4. *Relationship Between Professional Life and Teachers’ Instructional Behavior in Panabo Central District, Panabo City, when*

Table 3. Administrative Support in Panabo Central District, Panabo City

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Having a principal who supports my decisions and actions.	3.35	Moderately Extensive
Having a principal who is very supportive of the staff when new teaching methods are being implemented.	3.62	Extensive
Having the principal ensure that we have the necessary materials to carry out our teaching assignment.	3.89	Extensive
Having a school climate created by a strong leadership team and support from the staff helps to create a positive environment in which to teach.	4.25	Very Extensive
My school principal provides me with all kinds of support to complete my tasks.	3.29	Moderately Extensive
Having sufficient access to instructional technology, including computers, printers, software, and internet access.	2.28	Less Extensive
Having access to reliable communication technology, including phones, faxes, and email.	3.84	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.50	Extensive

Moderated by Administrative Support—The results of the analysis on the relationship between professional life and teachers’ instructional behavior in Panabo Central District, Panabo City, when moderated by administrative support, are presented in Table 10. Bivariate correlation analysis, using the Pearson product-moment correlation, was employed to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. There is a significant relationship between professional life and instructional behavior of teachers when moderated by administrative support, with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.788, p < 0.05$). With a correlation coefficient of 0.788 and a p-value less than 0.05, it is evident that administrative support significantly strengthens the impact of a positive professional life on instructional behavior. Administrative support acts as a

moderating variable, which means it influences the strength and direction of the relationship between professional life and instructional behavior. The high correlation coefficient suggests that administrative support not only enhances but also potentially magnifies the positive effects of a good professional life on instructional behavior. The findings align with Skaalvik and Skaalvik’s (2017) perspective that administrators who offer resources, clear communication, and emotional support foster a conducive work environment. Teachers who feel backed by their administration experience greater job satisfaction and reduced stress levels, which leads to more effective teaching practices. This support enables teachers to concentrate on their instructional responsibilities without being burdened by stress and dissatisfaction.

Table 4. Relationship Between Professional Life and Teachers’ Instructional Behavior in Panabo Central District, Panabo City when Moderated by Administrative Support

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Compassion Satisfaction	0.659*	0.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Revitalization	0.246*	0.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Comforting Thoughts	0.812*	0.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Overall Professional Life	0.788*	0.000	Significant	Reject H ₀

Note. *Significant at $p < 0.05$.
 Legend: Perfect Correlation ($r = 1.00$); Strong Correlation ($0.70 \leq r < 1.00$); Moderate Correlation ($0.30 \leq r < 0.70$); Weak Correlation ($0.00 < r < 0.30$); No Correlation ($r = 0.00$).

Adding more, the result in the table also shows that professional life in terms of compassion satisfaction, revitalization, and comforting thoughts have significant positive relationship with the teachers’ instructional behavior when moderated by administrative support with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.659$, $p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.246$, $p < 0.05$), and ($r = 0.812$, $p < 0.05$), respectively. The significant relationship between components of professional life—compassion satisfaction, revitalization, and comforting thoughts—and teachers’ instructional behavior is greatly enhanced by administrative support. This support acts as a critical moderator, strengthening the positive impacts of these professional life aspects on teaching effectiveness. According to Leithwood et al. (2019), schools with a collaborative and respectful atmosphere encourage teachers to engage more deeply with their instructional practices. Strong school leadership contributes to a favorable school climate, which in turn supports effective teaching and learning. When teachers feel valued and part of a supportive community, they are more likely to exhibit positive instructional behaviors.

3.5. *Moderating Effect of Administrative Support on the Interaction Between Professional Life and Teachers’ Instructional Behavior*

The moderating effect of administrative support (AS) on the interaction between professional life (PL) and teachers’ instructional behavior (IB) in Panabo Central District, Panabo City, was tested using hierarchical regression analysis. Results in Table 5 show that the Beta coefficients for the Step 1 analysis of professional life (PL) and teachers’ instructional behavior (IB) were = 0.105, S.E. = 0.056, $p < 0.05$; and administrative support (AS) and teachers’ instructional behavior (IB) were = 0.211, S.E.=0.049, $p < 0.05$. When professional life (PL) and administrative support (AS) were included as the only independent variables (without including an interaction term), the regression model explained 63.80% of the variance in teachers’ instructional behavior (IB) ($R^2 = 0.638$, $p < .05$). Moreover, Beta coefficients for the Step 2 analysis of professional life (PL) and teachers’ instructional behavior (IB) were = 0.384, S.E. = .031, $p < 0.05$; administrative support (AS) and teachers’ instructional behavior (IB) were = 0.177, S.E. = 0.048, $p < 0.05$; and moderator (PL*AS) and teachers’ instructional behavior (IB) were = 0.224, S.E.= 0.052, $p < 0.05$. Also, it was indicated that when an interaction between professional life (PL) and administrative support (AS) was added, the percentage of variance in teachers’ instructional behavior (IB) was 72.20% ($R^2 = 0.722$; $p < 0.05$)

indicated the independent contribution of each variable while controlling for the influence of others to create the regression equation for each analysis, after assuring significance by examining accompanying p-values. Hence, the interaction term accounted for an additional 8.40% of variance in the dependent variable ($R^2 = 0.084$). Based on the result, the null hypothesis was rejected as administrative support (AS) had significantly moderated the relationship between professional life (PL) and teachers' instructional behavior (IB) in Panabo Central District, Panabo City. Teachers who experience high levels of compassion satisfaction are more likely to engage in effective instructional behaviors. Tran and Smith (2020) suggest that when teachers feel appreciated and witness the positive outcomes of their efforts, they are more likely to adopt innovative and student-centered teaching methods. Administrative support enhances this dynamic by acknowledging and celebrating teachers' achievements, supplying the necessary resources for their continued success, and ensuring they feel valued and respected within the school community. Further, revitalized teachers are more energetic, enthusiastic, and willing to engage in creative and effective instructional practices. Ingersoll and Strong

(2018) observed that revitalized teachers are more inclined to embrace new challenges, incorporate various teaching methods, and foster a positive classroom atmosphere. Administrative support is crucial in this context, as it provides professional development opportunities, promotes a healthy work-life balance, and supplies resources that keep teachers refreshed and motivated. This support helps ensure that revitalized teachers can consistently maintain their high standards of instructional behavior. Furthermore, comforting thoughts help teachers maintain a positive and resilient mindset, which is essential for effective instructional behavior. As noted by Reeve (2016), teachers who have positive reflections about their work are better able to manage classroom challenges, maintain a positive learning environment, and implement consistent and effective teaching strategies. Administrative support enhances this by creating a supportive school culture where teachers' efforts are recognized, their well-being is prioritized, and they have access to resources and professional guidance. This supportive environment helps teachers translate their comforting thoughts into sustained instructional effectiveness.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section presents the researcher's conclusions and recommendations. The discussion is supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusion aligns with the statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate the influence of professional life on the instructional behavior of teachers when moderated by administrative support in elementary school teachers, using a non-experimental quantitative design with a descriptive-correlation technique. The researcher selected 197 elementary school teachers from Panabo Central District, Panabo City,

as respondents using a stratified random sampling method. The researcher utilized modified and enhanced survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure the high reliability and internal consistency of the instrument's items. Teachers' professional life in Panabo City got an overall mean of 3.29 with a moderately extensive descriptive rating. Additionally, teachers' professional life,

Table 5. Moderating Effect of Administrative Support on the Interaction Between Professional Life and Teachers’ Instructional Behavior in Panabo Central District, Panabo City

Step 1 – Teachers’ Instructional Behavior (IB)	B	Beta	S.E.	p-value
Professional Life (PL)	0.105	0.131	0.056	0.000
Administrative Support (AS)	0.211	0.078	0.049	0.000
<i>R² = 0.638 F-value = 117.884** p-value = 0.000</i>				
Step 2				
Professional Life (PL)	0.384**	0.576	0.031	0.000
Administrative Support (AS)	0.177**	0.126	0.048	0.000
Moderator (PL*AS)	0.224**	0.089	0.052	0.000
<i>R² = 0.722 F-value = 132.087** p-value = 0.000</i>				

Note. *Significant at $p < 0.05$. **Highly significant.
 PL = Professional Life; AS = Administrative Support; IB = Instructional Behavior.

in terms of compassion satisfaction, revitalization, and comforting thoughts, yielded mean scores of 3.23, 3.37, and 3.28, respectively. The instructional behavior of teachers in Panabo Central District, Panabo City, has an overall mean of 3.32, indicating a moderately extensive descriptive rating. Additionally, in terms of teachers’ instructional behavior, the mean scores for avoidance, caring, and repressive behaviors were 3.35, 2.99, and 3.62, respectively. Moreover, administrative support for teachers in Panabo Central District, Panabo City, has an overall mean of 3.50, with an extensive descriptive rating. Professional life has a significant positive relationship with teachers’ instructional behavior in Panabo Central District, Panabo City, when moderated by administrative support, with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.788$, $p < 0.05$). This means that as the extent of professional life changes, teachers’ instructional behavior also changes significantly when moderated by administrative support. Administrative support (AS) is a significant moderator of the interaction between professional life

(PL) and teachers’ instructional behavior (IB) in Panabo Central District, Panabo City. The analysis showed that when an interaction between professional life (PL) and administrative support (AS) was added, the percentage of variance in teachers’ instructional behavior (IB) was 72.20% ($R^2 = 0.722$; $p < 0.05$) indicated the independent contribution of each variable while controlling for the influence of others to create the regression equation for each analysis, after assuring significance by examining accompanying p-values. Hence, the interaction term accounted for an additional 8.40% of variance in the dependent variable ($R^2 = 0.084$).

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated: Teachers’ professional lives in Panabo City were extensive. Meanwhile, the professional life of teachers, in terms of compassion satisfaction, revitalization, and comforting thoughts, received extensive descriptive ratings. This suggests a balance between positive and negative experiences. This implies that while teachers may find some aspects of their job rewarding, they also encounter challenges that pre-

vent them from experiencing high levels of job satisfaction and professional fulfillment. Teachers' instructional behavior in Panabo Central District, Panabo City, was rated as moderately extensive. Teachers' instructional behavior, in terms of avoidance of negative, caring, and repressive approaches, falls into a moderately extensive rating. This shows that teachers employ effective strategies and techniques, but do not fully optimize these practices to their highest potential. This level indicates that while teachers are competent and deliver quality instruction, there may still be areas for improvement in terms of consistency, innovation, and responsiveness to student needs. Administrative support for the teachers in Panabo Central District, Panabo City, was rated as extensive. The result indicates that moderate administrative support ensures that teachers have access to essential resources, such as teaching materials, technology, and classroom supplies. While this support may not be comprehensive, it is sufficient to help teachers perform their duties effectively. On the one hand, the results showed that professional life has a significant positive relationship with teachers' instructional behavior in Panabo Central District, Panabo City, when moderated by administrative support. Administrative support acts as a moderating variable, which means it influences the strength and direction of the relationship between professional life and instructional behavior. The high correlation coefficient suggests that administrative support not only enhances but also potentially magnifies the positive effects of a good professional life on instructional behavior. On the other hand, administrative support had a significant moderating effect on the interaction between professional life and teachers' instructional behavior. This study emphasizes that administrative support is an undeniable factor that influences the interaction between professional life and teachers' instructional behavior. Moreover, administrative support had a significant moderating ef-

fect on the interaction between professional life and teachers' instructional behavior is guided by the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model and the principles of Instructional Leadership, which posit that administrative support serves as a key moderator, buffering the adverse effects of professional challenges, such as stress and workload, through the provision of essential job resources. Additionally, administrative support promotes teacher well-being and job satisfaction, fostering a favorable school climate and enhancing instructional effectiveness. This dynamic strengthens the relationship between teachers' professional commitment and their teaching practices, ultimately contributing to improved educational outcomes.

4.3. Recommendations—Policy makers should ensure adequate funding for schools to provide teachers with the necessary teaching materials, technology, and classroom resources. Moreover, policymakers should develop policies and initiatives that promote inclusive education and provide support for teachers to accommodate diverse learning needs. Promoting inclusive education and supporting teachers in accommodating diverse learning needs is not just a matter of social justice; it is a vital aspect of quality education and a reflection of the values of an inclusive society. These initiatives contribute to academic success, personal development, and the creation of a more equitable and harmonious world. School heads should allocate resources effectively to support teachers' instructional needs, ensuring they have access to materials and technology. They should also create opportunities for professional development, mentorship, and peer learning within the school. Creating opportunities for professional development, mentorship, and peer learning within schools is not just an investment in educators; it is an investment in the quality of education and the success of students. Elementary school teachers should take the initiative to seek professional development opportunities

and stay updated with best practices in education. Seeking professional development opportunities and staying updated with best practices in education is not only beneficial for educators but also crucial for ensuring the success and well-being of students. It empowers teachers to adapt, innovate, and excel in their roles, ultimately contributing to improved educational outcomes and a more dynamic and effective educational system. Future researchers should focus their research efforts on topics that directly impact teachers' professional life, instructional behavior, and administrative support. This is essential for evidence-based decision-making, continuous improvement, and the advancement of education. It has a far-reaching impact on the quality of teaching, teacher support, and ultimately, student success.

5. References

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